

FORDA FERSON: A PSYCHOLINGUISTIC ANALYSIS OF PERCEPTIONS AND COMMUNICATION FREQUENCY PATTERNS AMONG GENERATION Z SPEAKERS

Rosille R. Vitancor, Mary M. Tirariray, Rhyza Mary B. Mangmang,
Kier D. Labadan, John Louie P. Guimaras, LPT, MAEd-ELT

*Teacher Education Program, Christ the King College, Gingoog City, Misamis
Oriental, Philippines*

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12730401>

ABSTRACT

This qualitative study examined the perceptions and communication frequency patterns of Filipino Generation Z speakers regarding the slang phrase "forda ferson." Drawing insights from twenty key informants in Gingoog City, the research explored the frequency, contextual usage, associated meanings, and communicative contributions of the slang. Utilizing content analysis, the study revealed that "forda ferson" facilitated informal and playful communication, fostering camaraderie among speakers. While it effectively described actions and behaviors within social groups, its usage also posed comprehensibility challenges for those outside the immediate social and generational context. The findings underscored the dynamic nature of language evolution, indicating that the popularity of slang terms like "forda ferson" might decline over time. This research highlighted the interplay between language and social interaction, showcasing how slang emerged to fulfill specific communicative needs while reflecting broader societal shifts.

Keywords: *communication patterns, Generation Z, language evolution, slang, social interaction*

INTRODUCTION

Change is inevitable for both language and humans. Humans adapt to the current era they are living in and strive to keep up with present trends. Language, in turn, undergoes similar transformations. The inevitable change in language is manifested over time, highlighting that language continuously evolves with new sets of words being introduced to society (McWhorter, 2016). One intriguing aspect of language evolution is the emergence of slang words and phrases, which serve as markers of identity and belonging within particular communities (Alawiyah et al., 2023). This phenomenon is evident in the Philippines, a country where the creation and use of slang words, phrases, and expressions are prolific. The emergence of newly invented words has become an integral part of daily interactions and communication among Filipinos, particularly among the younger population.

Filipinos are known for their inventiveness and creativity in crafting new slang and expressions. The slangs created by Filipinos address their communication needs. The Filipino slang phrase "forda ferson" (or "For the Person" in its original form) exemplifies this linguistic creativity, demonstrating how Filipinos playfully develop new expressions to convey nuanced meanings (De Leon, 2022). This phrase, along with other slangs, illustrates how communication has evolved. The manner in which Filipinos communicate today differs from the past, with a noticeable shift in preferences for conveying ideas and information, particularly among younger generations.

For instance, the phrase "forda shopping ang ferson" describes a person who enjoys spending money on material things or who has just made a purchase. The combination of words in this phrase reflects the individual's status and attitude towards material possessions. This expression not only highlights personal preferences but also reflects the lifestyle, habits, and social group of the individual. It shows how language succinctly expresses nuances of identity and attitudes.

The phrase "forda ferson" originated on the video-sharing platform TikTok, thanks to content creator Chrishanna Luisa Olavidez Austria. In one of her videos, Austria, appearing flushed, greeted her followers with "mga ferson" and called herself a "drunk girl." Just before ending the video, she noticed her reflection and commented, "forda red girl." This video went viral and received 21 million views (De Leon, 2022). Subsequently, the phrase gained widespread popularity and usage among Filipino speakers, especially the younger generation. Its popularity has become a part of contemporary Filipino communication, showcasing its impact on modern linguistic practices.

The changes in language and communication reflect our technology-driven society. The phrase "forda ferson," which gained popularity on TikTok, demonstrates how social media platforms facilitate the rapid spread of newly invented words and expressions. Technology provides an avenue for innovative linguistic developments and their dissemination (Jebaselvi et al., 2023). If these terms are accepted and deemed relevant for communication, their spread from social media platforms to everyday usage becomes more prevalent.

Slang, characterized by its informality and distinctive use in communication, unites individuals within the same community who share cultural experiences. Generation Z, born between 1997 and 2012, exemplifies this trend. Exposed to today's technological advancements, Generation Z is at the forefront of creating and using new slang terms and expressions to convey their thoughts, ideas, and opinions (Almeida et al., 2020). Despite its informal nature, slang contributes significantly to the richness of language and communication (Mahapatra et al., 2022).

Furthermore, the use of slang terms and expressions reflects the interconnectedness of the society in which they are invented and used. The Philippines is known for its linguistic creativity, with people frequently altering language to signify specific actions or concepts. This dynamic linguistic expression involves adding or removing prefixes and suffixes, rearranging syllables, reversing words, and blending terms from different languages (Limos, 2019). For example, the slang "yorme" is an alteration of "mayor." This linguistic creativity dates back to the 19th century. In an interview with CNN Philippines, Jay-ar Igno, a Linguistics professor at the University of the Philippines, referred to this method of creating words as 'tadbalik.' Roy Cagalingan from the Komisyon sa Wikang Filipino noted that revolutionaries historically used this technique to conceal their identities. For instance, writer Marcelo H. del Pilar adopted the pseudonym "Plaridel" by rearranging the letters in his surname (De Guzman, 2017). Today, people enjoy inventing and using new words, often modifying existing words to make them their own and employing unconventional grammar or pronunciation to make them catchier.

The evolution of language, as evidenced by contemporary slang usage, demonstrates that language is not passive. The continuous addition of new words testifies to language's fluidity and adaptability to meet its users' needs (Knetemann, 2020). The way people communicated in the past differs from the present, with each era having its unique linguistic characteristics. In today's generation, where Filipino slang terms are popular, these expressions will eventually be documented in history, highlighting their contribution to communication and their role as a linguistic playground for experimentation with new words and expressions.

The adaptability of language enables individuals to use it as a tool for expression. Slang fosters a sense of community and belonging, allowing individuals to connect more deeply. The gradual shift in expression provides individuals with a sense of place, using newly invented words and expressions to build connections with others. Although some may take language for granted due to our innate ability to communicate, there is a need for a deeper understanding of language's profound impact on our daily lives.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to analyze Filipino Gen Z speaker's perceptions and frequency of usage patterns in communication focusing on the Filipino slang phrase "forda ferson". The implications and derived connotations of the phrase will be in the context of Filipino youth. This also sought to understand how language evolves and adapts to meet the

needs of its speakers. Furthermore, the paper intended to show how these slang terms can contribute to the daily communication of the Filipino Gen Z speakers.

Research Questions

The researchers developed four primary questions that were presented to the key informants aiming to address the demands of the study:

1. How frequently do the participants use the phrase “forda ferson”?
2. In what context is “forda ferson” typically employed?
3. What meanings or connotations are associated with the phrase “forda ferson”?
4. What is the implication of the phrase “forda ferson” to communication?

METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a qualitative research design to gather in-depth insights from twenty key participants, focusing on their personal perspectives regarding the topic.

To achieve the study's objectives, a psycholinguistic content analysis was employed. This method involves systematically categorizing and analyzing the responses of key informants to extract meaningful insights. Specifically, survey questionnaires featuring the phrase "forda ferson" were distributed to Filipino Generation Z speakers. These responses were coded for frequency of usage, contextual application, associated meanings or connotations, and their contribution to communication.

To ensure a representative sample of Generation Z speakers, the questionnaires were distributed electronically to individuals who were best suited to provide relevant answers. Researchers verified the compatibility of the informants' responses with the questionnaire items before accepting them. The sample comprised twenty individuals from Gingoog City. This study underscores the importance of eliciting authentic responses from participants, free from external influences or the opinions of others.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question 1: How frequently do the participants use the phrase “forda ferson”?

Table 1.

Frequency of participants' utilization of the phrase “forda ferson”

The frequency of usage of the phrase "forda ferson" among participants reveals a diverse pattern, indicating varying levels of integration of this phrase into their everyday lexicon. The data from Table 1 categorizes participants' usage into several distinct frequencies, which can be broadly grouped for analytical clarity.

Key Informants	Frequency of Use
R1, R14, R17	Rarely Used
R2, R3	Frequently Used
R4, R20	Never Used
R5, R12	Not Often
R6, R15	Seldom
R7	Couple of Times
R8	No Longer Used
R9, R10, R16	Occasionally
R11	Almost Everyday
R13	Daily
R18	Often Used
R19	Sometimes

A significant portion of participants, specifically those identified as R1, R14, R17, R5, R12, R6, R15, and R7, fall into the category of rare usage. This group, comprising 40% of the total respondents, reports using the phrase rarely, not often, or seldom. This suggests that while the phrase is known to them, it does not feature prominently in their regular communication.

Conversely, a smaller subset of participants, R2, R3, R11, R13, and R18, which constitutes 25% of the respondents, report frequent usage. This group includes those who use the phrase almost every day or daily, indicating that for them, "forda ferson" is a significant part of their daily vocabulary. The occasional users, including R9, R10, R16, and R19, represent 20% of the participants. These respondents use the phrase sporadically, which may imply contextual or situational usage rather than a habitual one. The data also shows that a minority of participants, specifically R4, R20, and R8, who make up 15% of the sample, never use the phrase or have ceased to use it altogether. This could reflect a variety of factors, such as personal preference, cultural shifts, or the phrase falling out of favor or relevance in their social circles. As noted by Fishman (1991), language usage patterns are often indicative of broader social dynamics and can reflect underlying cultural trends and shifts.

Overall, the distribution of frequency usage indicates that "forda ferson" is not uniformly used among the participants. The majority of respondents either rarely or occasionally use the phrase, suggesting it holds niche rather than widespread significance within the group. The presence of a subset of frequent users highlights that while the phrase may not be universally prevalent, it retains strong relevance for a particular segment of the participants. This pattern of usage could provide insights into social or linguistic trends within the group, indicating areas where the phrase retains cultural importance and areas where it is diminishing in relevance. As Labov (2001) posits, the dynamic nature of language and the different ways in which linguistic elements permeate individual communication practices are reflective of the adaptability and evolution of language in response to social contexts.

In conclusion, the varying frequency of "forda ferson" usage among the participants underscores the dynamic and context-dependent nature of linguistic

practices. This variability not only highlights individual differences in language use but also points to broader cultural and social factors that influence how and why certain phrases gain or lose prominence within a community.

Research Question 2: In what context is “forda ferson” typically employed?

Table 2.
Context of “forda ferson” utilization

Key Informants	Context of Use
R1, R3, R6, R9, R11, R13, R15	Describing or Referring to Someone
R2, R4, R10, R16	Informal Context
R5	Teasing a Person
R7, R8, R17, R18, R19	Conversations with Friends
R12	Expression of oneself
R14, R20	Highlighting a Gesture or Interest

The phrase "forda ferson" is employed in a variety of contexts, reflecting its versatility and the nuanced ways it integrates into different communicative scenarios among the participants. Analyzing the contexts of use as reported in Table 2 provides insights into the socio-linguistic dynamics and the cultural nuances underpinning this phrase.

A substantial proportion of participants, specifically R1, R3, R6, R9, R11, R13, and R15, use "forda ferson" when describing or referring to someone. This context suggests that the phrase is a descriptor, potentially highlighting characteristics, behaviors, or identities in a familiar or colloquial manner. The usage here aligns with common linguistic practices where certain phrases become shorthand for complex descriptions or shared understandings within a community (Eckert, 2012).

Another notable context for "forda ferson" is its use in informal settings, as indicated by R2, R4, R10, and R16. This grouping underscores the phrase's role in casual, everyday interactions, where formality is relaxed, and conversational norms are more flexible. Informal contexts often allow for greater linguistic creativity and the incorporation of colloquial expressions, which can enhance relatability and social bonding (Coupland, 2014).

Participants R5, R7, R8, R17, R18, and R19 employ "forda ferson" in conversations with friends or for teasing a person. This indicates that the phrase functions as a social tool to create in-group cohesion and shared humor. Such usage is common in peer group interactions, where language plays a crucial role in reinforcing social ties and mutual understanding (Meyerhoff, 2018). The teasing aspect, specifically noted by R5, further illustrates the playful and intimate nature of the phrase, suggesting it is used in environments where social bonds are strong, and mutual teasing is a form of affection or camaraderie.

R12 uses "forda ferson" for self-expression, indicating a personal and perhaps introspective application of the phrase. This context points to the flexibility of "forda ferson" in capturing individual identity or sentiment, aligning with the idea that language is a powerful tool for personal expression and the articulation of one's self-concept (Holmes, 2013).

Lastly, R14 and R20 use "forda ferson" to highlight a gesture or interest. This context implies a more action-oriented or demonstrative usage, where the phrase underscores specific behaviors or focal points in interaction. Highlighting gestures or interests suggests a performative aspect, where language is used to draw attention and convey significance (Kendon, 2004).

Overall, the diverse contexts in which "forda ferson" is used illustrate its multifaceted role in communication among the participants. The phrase's adaptability to describe people, function in informal and friendly interactions, serve as a teasing mechanism, facilitate self-expression, and highlight gestures or interests underscores its linguistic and social utility. The varied applications of "forda ferson" reflect its embeddedness in the socio-cultural fabric of the group, demonstrating how language evolves and adapts to meet the communicative needs of its users.

Research Question 3: What meanings or connotations are associated with the phrase "forda ferson"?

Table 3.
Meanings and connotations associated with the phrase "forda ferson"

Key Informants	Meanings and Connotations
R1, R19	Highlighting or Pointing out about a Person
R2, R11	Indirect Reference
R3	Classifying a Type of Person
R4	Originated from the phrase "for the person"
R5	Pointing out the Obvious or Complimenting
R6	Non-serious Alternative Reference
R7, R13	Referring to themselves or others
R8	Literal Meaning only
R9	Lessens Intimidation and Prevents Offense
R10	Describing a Feeling or Situation
R12, R14, R15	Expressing Interest
R16	Teasing and Joking
R17, R18, R20	Describing an Action

The meanings and connotations of the phrase "forda ferson" among participants demonstrate its rich semantic diversity and contextual flexibility. The data from the key informants, as shown in the table, provide a nuanced understanding of how this phrase operates within different communicative frameworks. Firstly, R1 and R19 use "forda ferson" to highlight or point out a person, indicating that the phrase serves as a tool for

drawing attention to specific individuals. This usage aligns with the general linguistic function of deictic expressions, which are used to point out or specify entities within a given context (Levinson, 2004). This deictic use underscores the phrase's role in social interactions where identifying and focusing on individuals is necessary.

R2 and R11 employ "forda ferson" as an indirect reference. This suggests a pragmatic function where the phrase is used to allude to someone without direct mention, perhaps to maintain politeness or subtlety. Indirect references are common in communication as they allow speakers to navigate social sensitivities and preserve face (Brown & Levinson, 1987). For R3, "forda ferson" classifies a type of person, indicating that the phrase has a categorical function. This connotation implies that "forda ferson" can be used to group individuals based on shared characteristics, contributing to the construction of social categories and identities (Agha, 2007).

R4 notes that the phrase originated from "for the person," highlighting its etymological roots. Understanding the origin of colloquial phrases is crucial as it provides insights into their initial meaning and subsequent semantic shifts (Tagliamonte, 2016). R5 uses "forda ferson" to point out the obvious or to compliment, indicating its dual role in emphasizing evident traits or actions and in expressing positive social evaluations. This usage aligns with the communicative function of compliments as social lubricants that enhance interpersonal relationships (Holmes, 1988).

R6 perceives "forda ferson" as a non-serious alternative reference, suggesting a playful or informal usage. This aligns with the concept of linguistic play, where language is used creatively and humorously to foster social bonding (Crystal, 1998). R7 and R13 use the phrase to refer to themselves or others, indicating a flexible personal reference. This flexibility in reference suggests the phrase's adaptability in various interactional contexts, enhancing its utility in everyday conversation (Goffman, 1981).

R8 applies a literal meaning to "forda ferson," indicating a straightforward interpretation without additional connotations. Literal usage can reflect the foundational understanding of the phrase before it acquires more nuanced meanings (Gibbs, 1994). R9 mentions that the phrase lessens intimidation and prevents offense, highlighting its mitigating function in communication. This usage is crucial in maintaining harmony and reducing potential conflicts in social interactions (Mcleod, 2023). R10 uses "forda ferson" to describe a feeling or situation, indicating its metaphorical extension beyond referring to people. Metaphorical language allows for more expressive and nuanced communication (Lakoff & Johnson, 1980).

R12, R14, and R15 employ the phrase to express interest, showcasing its role in indicating curiosity or engagement with a topic or person. Expressing interest is a key component of active and empathetic listening in communication (Rogers & Farson, 1987). R16 uses the phrase for teasing and joking, emphasizing its playful and humorous connotation. This usage aligns with the social function of humor in creating rapport and relieving tension (Hay, 2000). Finally, R17, R18, and R20 use "forda ferson" to describe an action, indicating its descriptive function in narrating or explaining behaviors.

Descriptive language is essential for effective storytelling and conveying detailed information (Tannen, 1989).

In summary, the diverse meanings and connotations of "forda ferson" among participants illustrate its multifunctional role in communication. Its applications range from direct reference and classification to playful teasing and metaphorical description, highlighting its semantic richness and adaptability within various social contexts.

Research Question 4: What is the implication of the phrase “forda ferson” to communication?

Table 4.

Implication of the phrase “forda ferson” to communication

Key Informants	Communication Implications
R1, R6, R16	Lightens Conversation
R2, R18	Sense of Camaraderie and Belonging
R3, R7, R8, R14, R17	Fun, Enjoyable, and Humorous Communication
R4, R10, R15	Enhances Communication
R5	Adds Spice, Emphasis and Character
R9	Prevents Misunderstanding and Intimidation
R11, R20	Causes Confusion and Communication Barrier
R12	Self-identification
R13	Good for Informal Conversations
R19	Makes Communication Casual

The phrase “forda ferson” carries significant implications for communication, influencing various aspects of interaction among the participants. The data from Table 4 provides a detailed overview of these implications, highlighting the multifaceted role the phrase plays in shaping communicative dynamics.

One of the primary implications, as noted by R1, R6, and R16, is that “forda ferson” lightens conversation. This aligns with the broader concept of linguistic strategies that reduce conversational tension and foster a more relaxed and congenial atmosphere (Norrick, 1993). By incorporating humor and light-heartedness, the phrase helps to ease social interactions and make them more enjoyable. Additionally, R2 and R18 indicate that the phrase fosters a sense of camaraderie and belonging. This suggests that “forda ferson” functions as a social glue, reinforcing group identity and cohesion. Shared linguistic practices, such as using specific phrases, are crucial in creating and maintaining social bonds within a community (Eckert, 2012). The sense of belonging facilitated by the phrase underscores its role in social integration and solidarity.

For R3, R7, R8, R14, and R17, “forda ferson” makes communication fun, enjoyable, and humorous. This indicates that the phrase adds an element of playfulness to interactions, which can enhance the overall communicative experience. Humor and enjoyment in communication are essential for building rapport and positive relationships

(Hay, 2000). The playful use of “forda ferson” likely contributes to a more vibrant and engaging conversational dynamic. R4, R10, and R15 highlight that the phrase enhances communication. This enhancement could be due to the phrase’s ability to convey nuanced meanings and add expressive depth to interactions. Enhanced communication through such phrases helps in articulating thoughts more effectively and enriches the interactional content (Gumperz, 1982).

R5 mentions that “forda ferson” adds spice, emphasis, and character to communication. This suggests that the phrase serves as a linguistic tool to emphasize certain points and make interactions more vivid and memorable. The use of distinctive phrases can inject personality and energy into conversations, making them more engaging and impactful (Crystal, 1998). R9 notes that the phrase prevents misunderstanding and intimidation. This implies that “forda ferson” can function as a mitigative device, softening potentially harsh statements and reducing the risk of miscommunication. Mitigative language strategies are vital in maintaining politeness and preventing conflicts in interactions (Brown & Levinson, 1987).

However, R11 and R20 observe that the phrase can cause confusion and act as a communication barrier. This indicates that not all participants may be familiar with or understand the phrase, leading to potential misinterpretations. The introduction of colloquial or context-specific language can sometimes hinder clear communication, especially if the interlocutors do not share the same linguistic background (Giles & Coupland, 1991). R12 points out that “forda ferson” aids in self-identification, suggesting that the phrase can be used to express personal identity or affiliation. Language is a powerful tool for self-expression, and specific phrases can serve as markers of identity and group membership (Holmes, 2013).

R13 finds the phrase well-suited for informal conversations, indicating its appropriateness in casual and relaxed settings. Informal language is characterized by its flexibility and creativity, and phrases like “forda ferson” enhance the informal communicative style (Coupland, 2014). Finally, R19 asserts that the phrase makes communication casual. This reinforces the idea that “forda ferson” contributes to a laid-back and informal conversational tone, which can be more accessible and less intimidating for participants. Casual communication often fosters openness and spontaneity, facilitating smoother and more dynamic interactions (Tannen, 1989).

In conclusion, the phrase “forda ferson” plays a significant role in communication among the participants, with implications ranging from lightening conversations and fostering camaraderie to enhancing communication and preventing misunderstandings. However, it also has the potential to cause confusion if not universally understood. These diverse implications underscore the complexity and multifaceted nature of linguistic expressions in social interactions.

Conclusions

The Filipino slang "forda ferson" provides substantial insights into its usage, social functions, and implications for language evolution and adaptation. Primarily employed in informal settings, this slang facilitates casual, playful communication among friends and close acquaintances, enabling individuals to express themselves freely without the constraints of formality. It functions not only as a linguistic tool but also as a social mechanism that enhances connections and fosters a sense of camaraderie among speakers.

Additionally, "forda ferson" is often used to describe actions, behaviors, and characteristics, either of oneself or others. This indicates that the slang provides an efficient way to share information about personal traits and actions within conversational contexts. Furthermore, it introduces a tone of playfulness and humor, contributing to more engaging and enjoyable interactions. This social function underscores its role in strengthening interpersonal bonds and creating a friendly atmosphere during communication.

However, the use of "forda ferson" is not without challenges. While it facilitates communication within certain social groups, it can lead to misunderstandings or misinterpretations among individuals unfamiliar with its meaning. This highlights a broader issue in language evolution: the balance between innovation and comprehensibility. As new terms and slang emerge, they can create generational or social divides, posing challenges for those outside the immediate social and generational group.

The findings reflect the dynamic nature of language. The varied frequency of informants using "forda ferson", ranging from occasional to seldom, indicates that the slang, once at its peak on social media, is gradually waning in popularity. This trend aligns with the natural life cycle of language, where terms may rise to prominence rapidly and then decline as language users shift their preferences. The fact that some individuals are aware of the slang but do not use it themselves further illustrates individual differences in adopting linguistic trends, influenced by personal communication needs and preferences.

Overall, "forda ferson" exemplifies how language evolves and adapts within social contexts. Slang terms emerge to fulfill specific communicative needs, reflecting the dynamic interplay between language and social interaction. While these terms can enhance communication within groups, they also highlight the challenges of maintaining mutual understanding across different social and generational boundaries. Ultimately, the evolution and adaptation of language are continuous processes shaped by the changing needs and preferences of its users.

Recommendations

The findings of this study on the Filipino slang "forda ferson" offer valuable insights into its usage and social functions. However, to advance our understanding of its implications for language evolution and adaptation, further research is recommended.

Future studies should aim to enhance depth by utilizing larger and more diverse samples to capture a broader spectrum of perspectives and usage patterns. This could involve investigating different age groups, social backgrounds, and regional contexts to identify variations and commonalities in the application of "forda ferson".

Moreover, researchers could adopt a longitudinal approach to observe how the usage and popularity of the slang evolve over time, providing a comprehensive understanding of its life cycle within linguistic trends. Examining the influence of digital media and cultural shifts on the dissemination and decline of slang terms could also yield valuable insights into societal changes.

In cases where the current findings suggest intriguing or unexpected outcomes, further research is essential to validate these results and explore underlying mechanisms. Such studies could delve into the cognitive and social processes that facilitate the adoption and diffusion of slang, thereby contributing to a more nuanced comprehension of language dynamics in contemporary society. This multifaceted approach will not only enrich scholarly discourse but also offer practical implications for understanding language evolution and adaptation in diverse cultural contexts.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to their participation, informed consent was diligently obtained to ensure voluntary engagement in the study. Additionally, stringent measures were implemented to guarantee the anonymity of informants, thereby fostering an environment conducive to open and uninhibited idea exchange. Participants were also informed of the study's objectives and purposes, ensuring transparency throughout the research process.

The well-being of participants was conscientiously safeguarded to prevent any conflicts of interest during the study. This approach promoted integrity and facilitated unbiased data collection, which is essential for rigorous and valid analysis. There was a meticulous avoidance of bias in the interpretation of findings, and results were exclusively utilized for research purposes, adhering strictly to scholarly standards.

Acknowledgements

The researchers extend sincere gratitude and appreciation to the following individuals and groups:

Firstly, to our research adviser, Mr. John Louie Guimaras, for his invaluable guidance, assistance, insightful comments, constructive suggestions, and provisions that significantly contributed to the completion and accomplishment of this study.

To the Gen Z speakers who generously participated in our study, we extend our heartfelt thanks. Their contributions were indispensable; despite busy schedules, they dedicated their time to share insights that greatly enriched our research.

We are deeply grateful to our parents, friends, and loved ones whose unwavering encouragement and continuous support were pivotal to the success of this research endeavor. Their support bolstered our efforts and inspired us throughout the process.

Furthermore, we extend thanks to all individuals who directly or indirectly assisted us in conducting this study. Each contribution, whether large or small, played a role in our research journey.

Above all, we express gratitude to our heavenly Father for granting us the wisdom, knowledge, and insight necessary to complete this study. His guidance and mercy were foundational to our ability to navigate challenges and accomplish our academic pursuits.

REFERENCES

- Agha, A. (2007). *Language and Social Relations*. Cambridge University Press. Retrieved from: <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2007-03763-000>
- Alawiyah, S., Zuriyati, & Lustiyantie, N. (2021). Slang language as representatives of social culture identity in film step up 2 the streets. *IJLECR (International Journal of Language Education and Cultural Review)*, 7(2), 204–213. <https://doi.org/10.21009/ijlecr.072.20>
- Almeida, F., Santos, J. D., & Monteiro, J. A. (2020). The challenges and opportunities in the digitalization of companies in a post-COVID-19 World. *IEEE Engineering Management Review*, 48(3), 97–103.
- Brown, P., & Levinson, S. C. (1987). *Politeness: some universals in language usage*. Cambridge University Press. Retrieved from: <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/1987-97641-000>
- Coupland, N. (2014). *Sociolinguistics: Theoretical Debates*. Cambridge University Press.
- Crystal, D. (1998). *Language Play*. University of Chicago Press.
- De Leon, P. (2022). "Forda" explanation ang ferson': And what does that even mean?. SunStar Publishing Inc. <https://www.sunstar.com.ph/amp/story/pampanga/opinion/de-leon-forda-explanation-ang-ferson-and-what-does-that-even-mean>
- De Guzman, N. (2017). The fascinating history behind Filipino slang. *Esquiremag.ph*. <https://www.esquiremag.ph/culture/the-fascinating-history-behind-pinoy-slang--a1729-20171107-lfrm>
- Eckert, P. (2012). Three waves of variation study: the emergence of meaning in the study of sociolinguistic variation. *Annual Review of Anthropology*, 41(1), 87-100.
- Fishman, J. A. (1991). Reversing language shift: theoretical and empirical foundations of assistance to threatened languages. *Multilingual Matters*.
- Gibbs, R. W. (1994). *The poetics of mind: figurative thought, language, and understanding*. Cambridge University Press.
- Giles, H., & Coupland, N. (1991). *Language: contexts and consequences*. Thomson Brooks/Cole Publishing Co.
- Goffman, E. (1981). *Forms of Talk*. University of Pennsylvania Press.
- Gumperz, J. J. (1982). *Discourse Strategies*. Cambridge University Press.
- Hay, J. (2000). Functions of humor in the conversations of men and women. *Journal of Pragmatics*, 32(6), 709-742.
- Holmes, J. (1988). Compliments and compliment responses in New Zealand English. *Anthropological Linguistics*, 30(4), 485-508.
- Holmes, J. (2013). *An Introduction to Sociolinguistics (4th ed.)*. Routledge.

- Jebaselvi, C. a. E., Mohanraj, K., Thangamani, A., & Kumar, M. (2023). The impact of social media on the evolution of language and communication trends. *Shanlax International Journal of English*, 12(1), 41–44. <https://doi.org/10.34293/english.v12i1.6725>
- Kendon, A. (2004). *Gesture: visible action as utterance*. Cambridge University Press.
- Knetemann, J. (2020). The fluidity of Language " Lingohut Blog. Lingohut Blog. <https://www.lingohut.com/blog/the-fluidity-of-language/>
- Labov, W. (2001). *Principles of Linguistic Change, Volume 2: Social Factors*. Wiley-Blackwell.
- Lakoff, G., & Johnson, M. (1980). *Metaphors We Live By*. University of Chicago Press.
- Levinson, S. C. (2004). Deixis and Pragmatics. In L. R. Horn & G. Ward (Eds.), *The Handbook of Pragmatics* (pp. 97-121). Blackwell Publishing.
- Limos, M. A. (2019). Filipino Slang: Decoding Street Words from the '70s through the'90s
- Mahapatra, G. P., Bhullar, N., & Gupta, P. (2022). Gen Z: an emerging phenomenon. *NHRD Network Journal*, 15(2), 246–256.
- Mcleod, S. (2023). Social Identity Theory in Psychology (tajfel & turner, 1979). *Simply Psychology*. <https://www.simplypsychology.org/social-identity-theory.html>
- McWhorter, J. H. (2016). *Words on the move: why English won't- and cant- sit still (like, literally)*. New York, Henry Holt and Co.
- Meyerhoff, M. (2018). *Introducing Sociolinguistics* (3rd ed.). Routledge.
- Norrick, N. R. (1993). *Conversational joking: humor in everyday talk*. Indiana University Press.
- Rogers, C. R., & Farson, R. E. (1987). Active Listening. In R. G. Newman, M. A.
- Tagliamonte, S. A. (2016). So Cool, So Smart, So Nice: The evolution of english intensifiers and the status of so. *Corpus Linguistics and Linguistic Theory*, 12(1), 59-88.
- Tannen, D. (1989). *Talking Voices: repetition, dialogue, and imagery in conversational discourse*. Cambridge University Press.